

Post-publication review of Zhang et al. Nature Communications 2017

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Summary

This review critiques the published claims of Zhang et al, Nature Communications 2017, based on our analyses of both published data and additional data shared with us by corresponding authors of the paper.

The main claim of the paper is given by its title, the observation of ‘Ballistic superconductivity in semiconducting nanowires’. ‘Ballistic superconductivity’ is a term coined by the authors not used elsewhere in the literature. According to some co-authors it means proximity induced superconductivity in a ballistic semiconductor nanowire. The claim of ‘Ballistic superconductivity’ is split into three subclaims which are illustrated by paper’s Figures, and described this way: ‘...a quantized conductance for normal carriers, a strongly enhanced conductance for Andreev reflecting carriers, and an induced hard gap with a significantly reduced density of states.’

Based on the data newly shared with us, we identify problems with each of these three subclaims (quantized conductance, enhanced Andreev conductance, and an induced hard gap), which together invalidate the main claim of the paper. The problems range from data manipulation and non-representative data selection, to failure to acquire (or, if acquired, to share with us) crucial data required to verify the subclaims. The data manipulation includes suppression of unfavorable features due to averaging and colorscale adjustment, as well as unjustified and undisclosed conductance recalibration.

We have circulated slides describing our analysis to all the co-authors and we understand that they may now be contemplating a correction or retraction of the paper. Based on the outcome of our analysis presented below, co-authors Vincent Mourik and Kun Zuo wish to remove their names even if the other authors decide not to retract the paper.

The additional data were provided to us in a mixture of numerical format (permitting our independent replotting) and laboratory-notebook-style powerpoints containing data as images, some of which we could not replot. Full data in spreadsheet form have not been shared. We thank the corresponding authors for sharing the additional data to help us interpret their claims. We were surprised that the total data acquisition time was unusually short, for a study of this magnitude. 5 devices were all studied in a period of 21 days¹. According to our assessment this should have taken much longer time to acquire all necessary data to allow the verification of claims.

The claim of quantized conductance

The paper claims the observation of quantum point contact (QPC) behavior for 5 devices. A single plateau-like feature in a plot of conductance versus bias voltage, is presented for each device, with the plateaus occurring precisely at the expected quantized value of conductance. In creating these Figures, however, the authors subtracted different values of series resistance for different devices. No justification for these subtractions was offered in the paper, nor were the different subtractions disclosed. Our detailed comparison of subtracted resistances documents these inconsistencies (see Table PPR1 and table PPR2 at the end of this document²). The problem with this approach is that in looking at a single plateau-like feature, it is always possible to place it at any value of conductance by subtracting a series resistance, a point we illustrate in Yu et al., Nature Physics 2021 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41567-020-01107-w>. None of the devices presented in Zhang et al, Nature Comm 2017 exhibit two or more plateaus - this would have eliminated the freedom to subtract any offset resistance so as to enable proof of quantized conductance.

¹Details of measurement duration:

Devices A, B, C and E were all part of the same fabrication batch and were cooled down together with 17 additional N-S junctions, i.e. there were a total of 21 N-S junctions. Not all data of all these devices have been shared with us, only data for devices A, B, C and E and a few additional data of other N-S junctions measured simultaneously. These data shared with us were taken between 23 September and 14 October 2015. It seems highly likely that this corresponds to the total measurement time, as it appears from laboratory notebooks shared with us that only limited data were taken on the remaining devices, likely in the same period. Also it appears most essential data covering all N-S junctions was taken rapidly in the first week of measurements, and subsequently 1 or 2 devices were studied in some more details for the magnetic field evolution of features inside the superconducting gap.

Device D was part of a different fabrication batch. We do not know if additional devices from this fabrication batch have been studied at low temperatures. The data of device D shared with us were all taken between 2 and 9 October 2015.

Taken together, this leads to our statement of a measurement period of 21 days (between 23 September and 14 October 2015).

² To avoid confusion with paper figures we label figures and tables in this memorandum as ‘Figure PPR1’, ‘Table PPR1’ etc.

Figure 2 & device B

Figure PPR1 Concealing unwanted features and manipulations for device B.

Top row, left: panel from paper, Figure 2a. Data is smoothed and colorscale is adjusted so that undesirable features are not easily visible.

Top row, right: the original plotting in the laboratory notebook shared with us by corresponding authors does in fact reveal these features (confirmed in independent replotting). These are: 1) a broad transient resonance crossing zero bias voltage, mimicking the theoretical Andreev enhancement, 2) a sharp resonance weakly dependent on gate voltage, typically associated in literature with an Andreev bound state and not consistent with a ‘hard gap’, 3) a sharp dip in the centre at zero bias, not expected in the naive theoretical models of ‘hard gap’ and Andreev enhancement.

Middle and bottom row: Figure 2d (bottom row, right) contains a fabricated quantized plateau. The averaging procedure of the authors applied to negative bias only shows a monotonously increasing conductance with a ‘hump’ caused by the transient resonance (middle row, left). Applied to positive bias, it shows a shallow and broad peak-dip structure caused by the transient resonance (middle row, right). Finally, to achieve the G_N curve of Figure 2d with an apparent plateau, both these curves were averaged (bottom row, left). There is no physical basis for this procedure and it is not applied elsewhere in the literature.

The authors also claim that the devices do not contain ‘quantum dots’ in support of their claim of ballistic transport. Contrary to this claim, we find features in additional data shared by the corresponding authors, which we interpret as quantum dots. Whether or not these features are due to quantum dots could have been the subject of a scientific debate: but the possibility of having such a debate was suppressed because of data manipulation. In particular, the colorscale of one plot was adjusted in a way that makes features reminiscent of quantum dots less visible, while two different datasets were averaged and combined, without disclosure, to create a fabricated plateau (see Figure PPR1).

In addition to the data manipulation discussed above, undisclosed data selection also served to obscure evidence of quantum dots. As many as 17 devices data from which have not been shown in the paper exhibit features similar to plateau-like regions, but with a less flat appearance (see Figure PPR2 and PPR3 for examples). The authors refer to these as ‘bad’, filled with ‘quantum dots,’ in lab notebooks that the corresponding authors shared with us in response to our request for additional data. Yet, the 5 devices that were actually shown in the paper have overall the same character. We therefore conclude that all the studied devices contained quantum dot states: a possibility obscured from the reader by the authors’ decision not to show the ‘bad’ devices in the paper.

Figure PPR2 Omitting non-ideal devices (I) Left: This device is called ‘Bad device - quantum dots’ in a laboratory notebook supplied when we requested additional data: the raw data behind the plot was not provided. Right: no comment on the quality of this device is given, but it was not included in the article. The features that make these ‘bad’ are resonant enhancements of conductance that look similar to those in published devices.

Figure PPR3 Omitting non-ideal devices (II) Out of 21 individual NS junctions, only 4 were selected for inclusion in the paper (green borders). These have a favorable appearance compared to the others, but all devices show evidence for localized states, incompatible with QPC. Graphs with magenta borders are most apparent but features fall on a continuum from most apparent to less apparent. These plots are from laboratory notebooks supplied by the corresponding authors when we requested additional data.

A final problem with the subclaim of quantized conductance is the authors' failure to acquire (or to share with us if they did acquire them) additional confirmatory data. It is well known (including to these authors, at least judging by their past publications), that it is possible to observe a flat conductance region (of the type presented in PPR1) that does not correspond to a true quantized plateau. Practitioners in the field therefore typically look for two other types of evidence, before claiming to have observed QPC behavior. One is "waterfall" plots acquired at high bias, and the other is magnetic field dependencies showing Zeeman splitting of plateaus. Both these types of evidence, as well as multiple plateaus in the same nanowire, are all provided in Kamhuber Nano Letters 2016, of which many of the key authors of Zhang Nature Communications are also co-authors, particularly, the three corresponding authors of Zhang Nature communications. Yet neither type of evidence is included in this paper.

The reason to examine the behavior of devices at high bias is two-fold. First, the previously measured subband spacing in InSb nanowires can reach 20 meV and hence high bias data can be used to definitively establish diamond-like regions of quantized conductance. Second, superconducting features occupy up to 2 meV in bias (the gap of NbTiN). Thus, conductance values are presumably affected by superconductivity and are not expected to be quantized. The corresponding authors provided the screenshot below from their laboratory notebook when we requested additional data, containing the phrase "*I think this is a plateau but needs higher bias!*" Yet higher bias data have not been shown. They were either not collected at the time of measurement, or not shared with us. Though the unusually short overall measurement

period (5 devices measured in 21 days, see Footnote 1) makes it unlikely that the data were obtained.

Figure PPR4 Page from digital powerpoint based laboratory notebook demonstrating that more data at higher bias would be required to claim QPC.

In addition to the apparent failure to study high bias, the authors fail to show magnetic field dependences confirming Zeeman splitting of plateaus into a 0.5 and 1.0 quantized plateaus (up to 2 T). Contrary to standard practice in QPC experiments in the same team, it appears that the authors did not acquire data at high magnetic fields. As for the low magnetic field data, we see superconducting features at zero-magnetic field associated with an ‘induced gap’ evolving into Andreev bound state features at finite magnetic fields. These data are largely not shown in the paper and this behavior is not discussed. We observe that the supplementary information contains a small amount of magnetic field dependent data for device B in supplementary figure 6. These data are briefly discussed in the final section of the main text. There the discussion omits the possibility that Andreev bound states are present, rapidly dispersing to low energy upon applying a magnetic field. This was a well-known phenomenon at the time of publication, associated with the presence of quantum dots. The data in supplementary figure 6 in combination with the features concealed in Figure 2 (see Figure PPR1 above) could be interpreted in an Andreev bound state framework (and are in fact present in all devices where magnetic field dependent data was obtained). This would constitute evidence of their origin from quantum dots states. Again, this was not presented or discussed in the published paper.

In summary, we find the claim of quantized conductance unsupported by the full data. The authors engaged in data manipulation, non-representative data selection, and unjustified conductance calibration. They also made significant conceptual errors, particularly failing to acquire a full diagnostic dataset that would have enabled them to prove they had observed quantized conductance.

The claim of enhanced Andreev conductance

Figures 2 and 3 are presented to support the authors' claim to have observed enhanced Andreev conductance in their devices. Figure 2a-d are shown to illustrate Andreev enhancement and ballistic transport in device B. This effect, according to the authors, manifests in conductance uniformly higher at voltage biases below the induced gap. In the case of Figure 2, this occurs at biases below 1 mV. However, in these and other data, conductance at low bias is only enhanced when a resonance in the gate passes through the low bias region; no uniformly enhanced conductance region is present. For instance, when we inspected the raw data of Figure 2a before processing (smoothing), we observed two broadened resonant peaks rather than an enhancement at low bias (see Figure PPR1). These resonances, as we discussed in the previous section, were not discussed in the paper as possibly originating from quantum dots, and the more obvious examples of such features in nominally identical devices, or in the same devices, were not shown.

In Figures 2 and 3, we also find that data obtained in measurements on the same device were used in different Figures, while data from different devices were presented within the same Figure. This gives the inaccurate impression that all the measured devices possessed all of the shown features. For example, Figure 3 combines plots from devices D and C. Color scale data from device C (Fig 3d) were used to compare to the numerical model in Fig. 3e. However, the line trace in the same figure (panel c) is from device D. **A reader would expect the authors to present the linetrace from the same device as the colorscale plot.** However, the analogous linetrace from device C is in Figure 2. That dataset is contradicted by a larger dataset exhibiting complicated non-monotonic features as function of gate which should translate into a mean free path parameter extracted from numerical modelling in Figure 3 that would be much shorter than claimed in the paper, and affect the validity of the numerical model used to confirm Andreev enhancement.

While there is no doubt that induced superconductivity affects measurements at low voltage bias, the full data point to quantum dot origins of low bias features, invalidating the claim of enhanced Andreev conductance in the ballistic open regime. In particular, the numerical model used by the authors does not apply to this regime and the numerical analysis does not describe the full data obtained. **In summary, we find the claim of enhanced Andreev conductance unsupported by the full data.**

The claim of hard induced gap

The authors claim to have observed a hard induced gap is based on plots of finite bias conductance versus zero bias conductance (which authors claim correspond to normal non-superconducting versus superconducting conductance, respectively). Similar plots, of GS vs GN, also appear in the now-retracted Zhang et al 2018 paper on Quantized Majorana Conductance. A fit of GS vs GN to a theoretical model is performed to assess the hardness of the induced gap. This is presented in Figure 4. The figure caption explains that the theory is *“agreeing perfectly with experimental data without any fitting parameter up to the dip on the right side of the plateau where the second channel starts conducting”*.

However, the GS vs GN plots are a result of unjustified data manipulation. The finite bias conductance GN was taken from a different data set, a procedure not disclosed in the paper. Each data set contains irreproducible features, so that combining them is not straightforward or justified. Furthermore, GN was taken at a low value of applied bias between 1 and 2 mV, very near the induced gap feature and within the bulk superconducting gap of NbTiN. Only with GN selected in this way, can a good fit of theory and ‘experimental data’ be obtained. **We conclude that the GS vs GN analysis in this paper is an unreliable composite, and therefore that the claim of hard induced gap is unjustified.**

Comment on numerical modeling

Another important claim in the paper is that of a long mean free path. From Figure 3 a mean free path of 10 microns can be inferred through a side-by-side comparison of the experimental data to a 10 micron mean free path model. This value is 50 times larger than any previously reported value for this quantity, and is in consonance with the claim of ‘ballistic’ transport. It also echoes numerical claims made in other papers by some of the same co-authors, where spin-orbit interaction was estimated to be nearly 100 times greater than what was previously measured in the same nanowires in the same group (Kammhuber Nature Communications 2017). As we already pointed out above, the undisclosed features that can be related to quantum dots make the numerical model not applicable to the experiment.

We believe that the model taken in isolation is likely accurate. However, the analysis that compares the model to the experimental data is invalid.

Overview of undisclosed data manipulations

Here we give an overview of undisclosed instances of data manipulation and errors that we have identified in this paper or that we were made aware of by the authors. This does not include the data selection issues or methodological concerns that we discussed above.

1. Figure 3c and Figure S1i, n: A charge jump is cut from the middle of the scan by omitting IV curves at 10 gate voltage values. The two sections of the dataset are then patched together, but the gate axis is left uncorrected, meaning that the left side of the scan does not correspond to the actual gate value.
2. Data from device D shown in figure 3c are based on a dataset (shown in S1i, n) where the conductance value of each datapoint got adjusted for the correct value of a set-up related series resistance, but the wrong value of series resistance was used for the corresponding bias voltage of each datapoint. This affects the curve in 3c.
3. The methods section states that all data were corrected for a 500 Ohm series resistance value due to the N contact interface resistance. This value is not motivated. This is important because the exact value of conductance is central to the paper.

4. Furthermore, this correction is omitted for device D, without justification. Including this and correcting for point 2 above leads to ~5% larger conductance compared to value shown in Figure 3c which appears to be close to the ideal quantized value.
5. It was not disclosed in the paper that all individual GN or GS curves shown in the paper (Figure 2d, e, Figure 3c, Figure 4a, d) are averaged over a bias window, with a size of 0.2 to 0.5 mV, in the case of GN sometimes combining positive and negative bias ranges. This step has consequences on the conclusions given the presence of transient resonances that shift in voltage bias and gate voltage. Discussion and disclosure of this data processing has not been made in the paper.
6. Figure 2a and 2d: color scale in panel 2a is chosen such that a resonance crossing through zero bias voltage is not clearly visible, nor a sharp resonance at finite bias and a sharp narrow dip at zero bias. The GN curve shown in Figure 2d is an average of data at both negative (-2 mV) and positive (+2 mV), a choice which results in the resonance being concealed. Plotting the trace of GN at +2 mV reveals the resonance. A similar issue affected the now retracted Zhang Nature 2018. See also Figure PPR1 above.
7. Figure 2e and S4a: curves stop just before the gate range where GS dips down further. A curve over a larger range compares less favourably to the numerical results.
8. The inset of Figure 4d is constructed by using the GN curve at $B = 0\text{T}$ for all B-field values. i.e. the same GN curve used for the main panel was replicated to generate the curves in the inset. To achieve this, the curve had to be shifted along the gate axis to account for a charge jump. This procedure assumes that GN does not depend on the magnetic field, which is not a justified assumption.

Conclusion

The claims of this paper depend on unambiguously establishing a QPC. However, a basic diagnostic dataset proving the presence of a QPC in the device was never acquired, or has not been shared with us if it was. The remaining evidence is ambiguous at best.

An impression of widespread occurrence of QPCs in the devices was created through 1) omitting most devices from the article, as they showed unambiguous evidence for localisation and quantum dot formation, 2) selecting data from the remaining 5 different devices, and spreading these over multiple main text figures claiming generic behaviour while no individual device could have supported all claims, 3) manipulation of these data through cropping, colorscale adjustment, and unjustified procedures such as conductance value tweaking (via arbitrary series resistance subtraction), averaging, charge jump removal, and re-using curves from one dataset in another dataset (GN vs GS curves).

Evidence for localization playing an important role (through the creation of broad transient resonances) was suppressed, leaving the two subclaims of Andreev enhancement and hard superconducting gap not supported.

The combination of both fundamental methodological problems and an extensive list of undisclosed manipulations convinces us that this paper is unreliable in its current form, and can never be corrected into a reliable scientific paper. We therefore recommend retraction of this article.

Table PPR1: Summary of series resistance treatment for the 5 devices shown in the article

Device	R _{series} set-up related (not disclosed)	Additional R _{series} included to account for e.g. contact resistances	Problem
A	7.14 kOhm	0.5 kOhm	<p>The additional series resistance value is an arbitrary choice. However, a non-zero value is strongly expected, of the order of at least 1 kOhm. When only a single quantized plateau is claimed, there is only a single known conductance value, and this additional series resistance acts as a single free fitting parameter.</p> <p>G_N is measured at too low bias voltage (because high bias voltage data is missing) where superconductivity still affects the conductance.</p>
B	7.28 kOhm	0.5 kOhm	
C	7.28 kOhm	0.5 kOhm	
D	<p>7.28 kOhm for voltage bias axis</p> <p>8.1 kOhm for conductance values</p>	0 kOhm	<p>1) No additional series resistance is subtracted, contradicting the statement in the methods section.</p> <p>2) The voltage bias axis was corrected for a different, wrong value of set-up related R_{series}.</p> <p>Including the same value of 0.5 kOhm as for the other devices, and correcting the error under 2), G_N is a few percent larger than the quantized value, deviating from the perfect quantization presented in Figure 3c. The authors recently claimed this is because the bias voltage at which G_N is measured is too small, and G_N includes a portion of superconductivity related conductance.</p>
E	7.42	0.5 kOhm	See comment under A-C

Table PPR2: Breakdown of set-up related series resistances for the 5 devices shown in the article. Note we could somewhat verify these values from laboratory notebooks and our own recollections about the experimental set-ups in the team, but ultimately we have to trust the 2015 reporting and 2021 correspondence with the lead authors.

Device	Set-up	DC line resistance	RC filter resistance	Current amplifier impedance	Total
A	Leiden Cryogenics wet fridge 'Big Frossati'	0.14 Ohm (2x Cu line)	4.0 kOhm	3.0 kOhm	7.14 kOhm
B	Leiden Cryogenics wet fridge 'Big Frossati'	0.28 Ohm (1x Cu line, 1x Mn line)	4.0 kOhm	3.0 kOhm	7.28 kOhm
C	Leiden Cryogenics wet fridge 'Big Frossati'	0.28 Ohm (1x Cu line, 1x Mn line)	4.0 kOhm	3.0 kOhm	7.28 kOhm
D	Leiden Cryogenics dry fridge 'CF-900'	0.1 Ohm (2x Cu line)	5.0 kOhm	3.0 kOhm	8.1 kOhm
E	Leiden Cryogenics wet fridge 'Big Frossati'	0.42 Ohm (2x Mn line)	4.0 kOhm	3.0 kOhm	7.42 kOhm